

Evaluation of Integrating LLMs with Telemetry Data from Optical Networks

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Abstract—This demo explores how to improve network management by integrating LLMs with telemetry data using process mining and RAG. This combination provides deeper network insights, task automation, and user-friendly interfaces. The approach aims to identify failures and optimize performance, using abstracted or updated data to overcome LLM limitations.

Index Terms—Large Language Models, Process Mining, Retrieval Augmented Generation, Telemetry, Optical Networks

I. MOTIVATION

Modern optical networks are crucial to offering high-bandwidth services and low-latency communication systems that require exceptional performance and reliability. Effective monitoring, especially through telemetry, is essential for managing these complex networks, which often include disaggregated and multi-vendor components [1]. Telemetry provides real-time data collected from various observation points, offering critical insights into network behavior and performance [2]. This real-time visibility helps operators identify potential issues, optimize resource allocation, and respond proactively to dynamic conditions. Telemetry can detect subtle performance degradations, known as *soft failures*, which traditional methods might miss [3]. By continuously streaming detailed performance data, telemetry enables operators to address issues before they escalate, ensuring smooth network operation.

Large Language Models (LLMs) have revolutionized various fields, including data analysis and natural language processing, with their ability to process vast amounts of textual data, answer complex questions, and even generate code. However, LLMs may lack current or specific information due to the time-consuming and labor-intensive nature of retraining them. Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) addresses this by allowing the LLM to access and use relevant information from external sources, providing current data without retraining [4]. This is particularly important in control management where real time data and updates are needed. Besides, process mining offers a powerful technique for analyzing event data, like that provided by telemetry, to understand and improve

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processes. By applying process mining to telemetry data from optical networks, valuable insights into network behavior can be gained, enabling the identification of both inefficiencies and performance optimization.

This demonstration explores how integrating LLMs with optical network telemetry, along with auxiliary tools like process mining and RAG, can lead to improved autonomous network control and management. Specifically, by combining the LLMs data processing power with the analytical capabilities of process mining, network operators attain deeper insights into network behavior, automate tasks, optimize performance, and ensure the reliability of critical communication infrastructures. The demonstration will showcase specific use cases and examples, highlighting practical applications of this approach.

II. DEMO DESCRIPTION

The integration of LLMs with RAG and process mining tools (e.g., PM4PY), depicted in Fig. 1, offers several compelling advantages for analyzing telemetry data in optical networks. On the one hand, by accessing external, current, and relevant information, RAG improves the accuracy of LLM responses and ensures that LLMs have the necessary context to answer queries correctly. On the other hand, one key benefit is the abstraction provided by process mining tools to preserve privacy. Due to the inherent limitations of LLM context windows, which cannot handle the massive volume and complexity of raw event logs or detailed process model representations, abstraction techniques condense this information into more manageable formats. This allows LLMs to act as intermediaries, translating natural language queries from users into SQL queries that can be executed against the telemetry data without directly exposing the raw data. This approach safeguards sensitive network information while still enabling effective data analysis, which is crucial in today’s environment where data privacy is paramount.

Another significant advantage is the creation of user-friendly interfaces for non-technical users. Traditionally, interacting with process mining tools required specialized knowledge and expertise. However, LLMs enable the development of intuitive interfaces where users do ask questions in natural language, without needing to understand complex query languages or process mining concepts. This democratizes access to valuable network insights, allowing a broader range of personnel to contribute to network management and optimization. Furthermore, process mining tools excel at processing large quantities

Fig. 1. Integration of LLMs, RAG, process mining and telemetry data

of telemetry messages generated by modern optical networks. In fact, they effectively summarize the data, identify patterns, and generate hypotheses for further investigation. For example, a process mining tool combined with an LLM could analyze telemetry data for anomaly detection or identify patterns indicating an emerging traffic bottleneck. The results could then be used to analyze the specific processes and network paths contributing to the bottleneck, triggering selected actions to mitigate the issue.

A. Innovation

This demonstration provides tangible proof that the integration of LLM into optical network control is not only feasible but also beneficial. To this end, collected telemetry data collected is analyzed with LLM and process mining, and the resulting information can be used to trigger automated actions for network optimization and remediation. Specific advantages of such an integration includes the creation of user-friendly interfaces that allow non-technical users interacting with process mining tools using natural language and translating their queries into executable SQL queries. This simplified access to valuable telemetry data enables a wider range of stakeholders to participate in the network control and management. Additionally, the combination of telemetry data, RAG, process mining, and LLMs can identify and effectively respond to network issues leading to both enhance network reliability and favor real-time operations.

III. DEMO CONTENT AND IMPLEMENTATION

The demonstration shows how LLMs analyze and understand updated and complex telemetry data, providing actionable insights for optical network management. One key objective is to retrieve relevant information from external sources to generate LLM responses using RAG (orange lines in Fig. 1). Another key objective demonstrates the value of process mining for structuring and analyzing raw telemetry data (blue lines in Fig. 1). This emphasizes the importance of abstraction techniques to bridge the gap between vast telemetry data and LLMs' limited context windows, showcasing LLMs' ability

to generate insights from abstracted process mining results, and empowering network operators to identify performance bottlenecks, potential failures, and optimization opportunities.

The demonstration utilizes a telemetry dataset containing selected information on OSNR and BER measurements at the optical transceivers, input and output power at intermediate amplifiers, and a "Failure" field indicating entries recorded during a simulated failure scenario. The audience will be able to interact through a ChatBox asking, for example, queries such as *what are the BER, OSNR levels, or Input or Output power thresholds that lead an optical connectivity service to be considered failed*. The entire demonstration will run on a laptop with all components set up in advance.

Both RAG and process mining have some common procedures in their operation. **Data Loading:** The dataset is loaded and pre-processed for use. For process mining analysis using the PM4PY library [5], Pandas DataFrame is used, the Unix timestamps are converted to a human-readable format and checked for either missing values or inconsistencies. RAG includes splitting, indexing, and embedding external sources as part of its process. **Prompting LLM:** A tailored prompt is crafted for the LLM, incorporating the generated abstractions in the case of process mining or retrieved information in the case of RAG. This prompt includes specific questions to extract insights about the failure scenario, such as thresholds for various metrics and combinations of attribute values indicative of failures. **LLM Interaction:** The prompt is sent to the LLM, and its responses are displayed.

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